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CHANGES IN OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE OF FEMALE POPULATION IN BAREILLY DISTRICT: A GEOGRAPHICAL STUDY

Geeta Devi, Seema Tiwari and Dilip Kumar Chaudhary

Abstract

The Distribution of the population according to different types of occupations is referred to as the occupational structure. In this paper we made an attempt to understand the participation of women in paid work in Bareilly District based on secondary data for both the Census years 2001 and 2011. The data has been collected from the secondary sources (mainly from District Census Handbook of Bareilly District, 2001 and 2011). The data has been analysed in MS excel software and the maps has been prepared on ArcGIS 10.7. The analysis of the data showed a spatial variation among the different blocks of Barielly District. The major finding reveals that, the trend in literacy is increasing whereas the workforce participation has been decreasing during the last decade due to the population increase which leads to the declination of job opportunities. The decreasing workforce in cultivators has been due to the changing in the family structure which causes fragmentation of land and due to which many cultivators either sold their land or given it on lease. The decrease in agricultural labourers has been attributed due to the increasing in other workers category due to higher literacy and less wages in agricultural activities. The increase in household workers category and others workers has attributed due to the change in living standards due to higher educational level. The government has also provided job opportunities in many sectors other than primary sectors so the engagement in other activities has an increasing trend.

Introduction

When we talk about occupation it implies the trade or profession of a person. The nature of the economic progress of a country is determined by it. Occupations depend upon the degree of economic development of the country. Within a certain economic activity, a distribution in the proportion of the active population is called occupational structure (Dasgupta and Goldar, 2005; Verma, 2020). Many aspects of the population influence the occupational structure in a region.

The occupational structure describes the country's working force, dependency load, employment and unemployment. It clearly shows the working and non-working populations in an area of a country. The occupational structure also influences the socio-economic development of the region (Kaur, 2016; Sors et al, 2015).

Women are less likely to work for income or actively seek work. The global labor force participation rate for women is just over 50% compared to 80% for men (International Labour Organization, 2020) while in India As per Census 2011, the workforce participation rate for females is 25.51% against 53.26% for males. Rural sector has a better female workforce participation rate of 30.02% compared with 53.03% for males whereas for urban sector. In a primarily agricultural country like India women play an especial role in rural economic activities in earning a livelihood for the family. We see that the largest number of working women in India had been engaged in farming operations either as cultivators or as agricultural laborers. They take up a wide variety of activities like sowing of seeds, transplanting, weeding, harvesting, preparation of compost and manure pits, application of manures, storage of seeds and food grains (Nath, 1970; Chakravarthy, 1975) but now the situation are changing and females are working as skilled workers (Nayyar, 1987). The increase of female education are helping to improve the women workforce participation and it resulted in delayed marriage, delayed fertility behavior, happy and healthy family, better nurturing of children, and better living standards of the family (Devi and Tiwari, 2019; Heath and Jayachandran, 2017). The literacy rate and level of education of females in every state of India is increasing with each passing year but the relation between the literacy rate and work participation not changing as much. As the the gap between rich and poor is increasing so as the gender inequality in workforce and social participation is also increasing due to the social dogmas (Fletcher et al, 2017; Kapos et al, 2014; Tripathy and Raha, 2019). The higher educated women have greater chances to be employed in formal sector or skilled workers category in comparison to the uneducated or less educated women which minimizes the gap between male and female in educational attainment and labor force participation (Lahoti and Swaminathan, 2013; Ince, 2010).

Study Area

The district Bareilly is a part of the Rohilkhand division, named after its headquarter city, i.e., Bareilly, founded in 1537 by Bans Deo and Bareldo, the two sons of Jagat Singh Katehriya, a Rohela Rajput. Bareilly district is also known as Bans-Bareilly (also Bareli) due to its big bamboo market. areilly district is situated northwest of U.P., which touches the boundary of the state Uttaranchal. It lies

between latitude 28° 01' and 28° 51' north and longitude 78° 58' and 79° 47' east. The district is a part of the southern upper Ganga Plain. Its maximum length from north to south is about 96 kilometers, and its maximum breadth from east to west is about 27 kilometres. It is surrounded in the north by Nainital and district Udham Singh Nagar, east lies the district Pilibhit, and southwest district Badaun bounds it. Ram Ganga forms the natural boundary between the two districts for about 30 km. On the west lies the district of Rampur. The total area of the district is 4,120 sq. km. The district has been divided into six tehsils and fifteen development blocks; Baheri, Bhadpura, Bhuta, Bithrichainpur, Faridpur, Fatehganj west, Alampur Jafrabad, Kyara, Majhgwan, Meerganj, Nawabganj, Ramnagar, Richha, and Shergarh. Bareilly district is well connected by Railways & Roadways. National Highway 24, state highway 33, and many metaled roads make connectivity easier through the district. Ramganga is the main river of the district, and Bahgul, Shankh, Devrania, Nakatia, and Kailasi is some other rivers flowing in the district. Bareilly is one of the 100 Smart Cities being developed in India. Bareilly is a fast-growing city known as the counter-magnet city because it is equidistant from New Delhi and Lucknow and has a lot of potential for setting up industries and attracting people for employment. According to the 2011 census, the district has 31 towns and 2051 villages. Out of 4,448,359 persons in the district 64.7 percent (2,879,950) lives in the rural areas and 35.3 percent (1,568,409) in urban areas rural areas and 35.3 percent (1,568,409) in urban areas.

Objectives

- (1) To find out the block-wise variations in female workforce participation in different economic activities, and,
- (2) To study the change in workforce participation in the study area.

Database and Methodology

This paper is based on secondary data collected from the District Census Handbook 2001 and 2011. The whole population of any area is divided into the working and non-working population. The occupational structure is categorized into 4 categories i.e. cultivators, agricultural labourers, household industry workers and Other workers. For this study, development blocks have been taken as a study unit for showing the distribution and share of different occupations in 2001 and 2011. Decadal changes are also calculated for showing the growth in the individual occupation in any particular spatial unit (blocks). All data are tabulated and represented in a systematic way for this spatial analysis of occupational

structure in the district. Statistical techniques of percentage and ratios are used for the comparative study of blocks. Relevant data is calculated on Microsoft excel software and choropleth maps are prepared with the help of ArcGIS software.

Results and Discussion

Working Population

In Bareilly district during 2001, 31.70 percent total population are working population in which 49.62 percent are male while only 10.91 percent are females. While in 2011, 31.05 percent population are engaged in different kind of works for their livelihood. Data shows that according to census 2011, out of 31.05 percent working population, 48.25 percent are male workers while only 11.56 percent are female. Maximum change occurs in female working population. It recorded 27.20 percent positive change while 11.56 percent and 16.23 percent male population increased during this period. Maximum working females was found in Baheri block in 2001, while in 2011, Nawabganj block have maximum proportion of female working population. Maximum change occurred in Bhuta (231.71%) block change while lowest change in female working population was found in the Baheri (-68.13%) block from 2001 to 2011. Out of 15 blocks eleven blocks (Bhuta, Bhadpura, Nawabganj, Bithrichainpur, Bhojipura, Kyara, Meerganj, Fatehganj West, Ramnagar, Majhgawan and Faridpur) recorded positive changes in female working population while four blocks (Baheri, Shergarh, Alampur Jafarabad and Richha).

Cultivators

According to census, a person is classified as cultivator if he or she is engaged in cultivation of land owned or from government or from private persons or institutions for payment in money, kind or share. Cultivation also includes effective supervision or direction in cultivation. Cultivation involves ploughing, sowing, harvesting and production of cereals and millet crops such as wheat, paddy, jowar, bajra, ragi, etc., and other crops such as sugarcane, tobacco, ground-nuts, tapioca, etc., and pulses, raw jute and kindred fiber crop, cotton, cinchona and other medicinal plants, fruit growing, vegetable growing or keeping orchards or groves, etc. (Census, 2011). According to the Census of India 2001, the total proportion of female cultivators in the working population was 42.27 per cent which decreased to 20.12 per cent in 2011, indicating the increase in secondary and tertiary occupations in the district in the last decade. The highest proportion of female cultivators was found in Shergarh

(67.73%) and Ramnagar (33.56%) block in 2001 and 2011 respectively while the lowest proportion was found in Alampur Jafarabad (25.22%) and Bhojipura (11.24%) block in 2001 and 2011 respectively (Table 1). The proportion of cultivators in Alampur Jafarabad, Bhuta and Bithrichainpur blocks was very low (<30%) followed by blocks Baheri, Nawabganj, Bhojipura, Bhadpura, Ramnagar, Majhgawan, Kyara, and Faridpur which indicated medium (20-25%) distribution of female cultivators in 2001. A total of 4 blocks, Richha, Shergarh, Meerganj and Fatehganj West reported high (>49%) proportion of female cultivators in working population in 2001, while in 2011, not a single blocks lies in this category. Which is indicating a sharp decrease in the proportion of female workers involved in cultivation. This decrease can be attributed to growing secondary and tertiary occupations in the district, subsistent agriculture, increasing infrastructure, education and urbanization.

Table-1: Distribution of Female Cultivators and Agricultural Labourers (2001-2011)

Blocks	Cultivators			Agricultural Labourers		
	2001	2011	Change (2001-11)	2001	2011	Change (2001-11)
Baheri	38.03	18.54	-84.46	28.69	34.38	-61.81
Shergarh	67.73	20.54	-76.89	20.83	22.74	-16.8
Richha	50.78	25.94	-49.6	29.5	20.79	-30.46
Bhojipura	48.65	11.24	-55.34	27.5	16.74	17.64
Bithrichainpur	28.36	18.79	65.71	21.06	12.24	45.31
Kyara	32.29	16.09	1.68	17.15	17.15	104.07
Mirganj	52.18	24.55	-17.11	29.74	28.64	69.66
Fatehganj West	51.15	13.24	-69.45	23.77	14.62	-27.44
Ramnagar	45.55	33.56	39.87	24.83	24.85	90.01
Majhgawan	39.98	31.73	96.94	20.97	19.19	127.08
Aalampur Jafarabad	25.22	24.64	-25.56	17.7	27.37	17.81
Nawabganj	40.83	11.77	-26.8	21.56	17.35	104.23
Bhadpura	39	19.38	60.35	25.45	20.94	165.61
Bhuta	27.95	15.03	78.34	15.12	18.71	310.54
Faridpur	35.05	18.24	21.22	17.7	21.6	184.16
Total	42.27	20.12	-39.47	23.51	20.8	12.53

Source: District census handbook, Bareilly, U.P.

Out of 15 blocks, eight blocks of the study area witnessed a decrease in the share of female cultivators in the last decade (Table 1 & Figure 1). The decadal change in cultivator population is negative (-39.47%) in Bareilly district. There were only seven blocks (Bithrichainpur, Kyara, Ramnagar, Majhgawan, Bhadpura, Bhuta and Faridpur) in which the change in cultivators was positive. The reasons for this positive change are productive landholdings, fertile soil and irrigational facilities. Richha, Nawabganj, Alampur Jafarabad and Meerganj blocks reported low negative change (Less than -50 to 0%), while Shergarh, Bhojipura and Fatehganj west blocks were having a high negative (More than -50%) change (Figure 2). Baheri (- 84.46%) block had the highest negative growth in female cultivator population, this is due to the inclination of youth in education and service sector and urban migration among others.

Agricultural labourer

A person who works on another person's land for wages in cash or kind or share is regarded as an agricultural labourer. She/he has no risk in the cultivation, but merely works on another person's land for wages. An agricultural labourer has no right of lease or contract on land on which she/he works. The proportion of female agricultural labourers in the total working population was 23.51 per cent in 2001 that decreased to 20.80 per cent in 2011 (Table 1). The lowest proportion of female agricultural labourers was found in Bhuta (15.12%) and Bithrichainpur (12.24%) in 2001 and 2011 respectively, because of the presence of tertiary activities and decreasing agricultural activities. The highest proportion of agricultural labourers was reported in Meerganj (29.74%) and Baheri (34.38%) blocks in 2001 and 2011 respectively, due to the predominance of agriculture and lack of service sector. During 2001, four blocks have high proportion of female agricultural labourers while in 2011 only three block lies in this category. North and Eastern blocks (Baheri, Richha, Meerganj and Bhojipura) of the district corresponded to high (>26%) level of agricultural labourers in 2001, while the southern blocks (Kyara, Bhuta, Alampur Jafarabad and Faridpur) were having low (<19%) share of these workers (Table 1 & Figure 1). The decadal change in agricultural labourers was 12.53% from 2001 to 2011. The highest decadal change was observed in Bhuta (310.54%) block while the lowest was in Baheri (-61.81%) block. Four blocks (Baheri, Shergarh, Richha and Fatehganj west) showed negative growth in female agricultural labourers in the last decade (Fig.-1), the reason being the modernization of agriculture, urban migration and growing service sector in nearby areas. 8 blocks were having less growth than the district growth regarding these labourers.

Household Industry Workers

Household industry is defined as an industry conducted by one or more members of the household at home or within the village in rural areas and only within the precincts of the house where the household lives in urban areas. The larger proportion of workers in household industry should consist of members of the household. The industry should not be run on the scale of a registered factory which would qualify or has to be registered under the Indian Factories Act and should be engaged in manufacturing, processing, servicing and repairs of goods. The activity relate to production, processing, servicing, repairing or making and selling of goods. It does not include professions such as a pleader, Doctor, Musician, Dancer, Waterman, Astrologer, Dhobi, Barber, etc. or merely trade or business, even if such professions, trade or services are run at home by members of the household. According to the census 2001, the proportion of female household industry workers was 9.91 per cent which increased to 24.48 per cent of the total working population in 2011. The highest proportion of these workers were reported in Bhuta (28.87%) block in 2001 while in 2011, Shergarh, Fatehganj West, Bhojipura, Nawabganj, Bithrichainpur and Bhuta lies in this category (Table 2 & Fig. 2). Similarly, the lowest proportion was found in Shergarh (3.16%) in 2001 and Ramnagar (10.42%) in 2011, which shows their dependence on agriculture. The increasing workers in this category during the last decade shows that smaller household activities and production has increased in the district. All blocks reported increased in female household workers during 2001 to 2011. Shergarh, Nawabganj, Bhojipura, Fatehganj West, Bithrichainpur and Bhuta blocks of the district were having a much higher proportion of household female workers in 2011 than their previous proportion, due to closeness with urban centres. These urban centers provide households works for female workers. The decadal change from 2001 to 2011 in Bareilly district in terms of female household industry workers was 214.30 per cent, indicating positive growth. All the 15 blocks reported positive growth rate of female household workers during this time period. The Bhojipura (673.10%) block showing the highest growth, while Alampur Jafarabad (14.28%) being the lowest growing block in the district (Table 2 & Figure 2). There were three blocks (Nawabganj, Shergarh and Bhojipura) in which the decadal change of household workers was high (343 to 508%) to very high (>508%), the main reason of this higher growth can be attributed to the nature of economic activities moving rapidly from agriculture to industries, good infrastructure and availability of market and town. Seven block recorded medium growth rate during this period. While the

Fig. 1

decadal change in Kyara, Baheri, Richha, Ramnagar and Alampur Jafarabad blocks was low (<178%) due to the availability of fertile land and other tertiary occupation. Jari work is the major households industry in Bareilly district. Villages near urban centres more work and good wages for households as compare to villages which situated far from urban centres.

Table-2: Distribution of Female Household Industry Workers and Other Workers (2001-2011)

Blocks	Household Industry Workers			Other workers		
	2001	2011	Change (2001-11)	2001	2011	Change (2001-11)
Baheri	3.67	17.77	54.46	29.61	29.31	-68.45
Shergarh	3.16	26.36	536.28	8.28	30.35	179.35
Richha	6.6	16.66	149.08	13.12	36.6	175.14
Bhojipura	9.34	37.36	673.1	14.51	34.66	361.54
Bithrichainpur	23.87	31.79	233.16	26.71	37.18	248.14
Kyara	18.51	20.01	120.55	32.05	46.75	197.58
Mirganj	6.22	12.56	255.56	11.85	34.24	409.02
Fatehganj West	13.54	33.17	188.98	11.53	38.97	298.56
Ramnagar	16.64	10.42	18.91	12.99	31.16	355.44
Majhgawan	10.26	18.16	338.95	28.78	30.92	166.59
Aalampur Jafarabad	10.87	16.31	14.28	46.2	31.68	-47.76
Nawabganj	17.99	31.83	349.04	19.61	39.06	405.57
Bhadpura	18.77	24.96	329.19	16.79	34.72	567.37
Bhuta	28.87	32.03	268	28.06	34.23	304.64
Faridpur	19.27	24.57	196.93	27.97	35.58	196.23
Total	9.91	24.48	214.3	24.31	34.61	81.09

Source: District census handbook, Bareilly, U.P.

Other Workers

A person, who has been engaged in some economic activity during the last year of reference period but not as a cultivator or agricultural labourer or worker in Household Industry. The type of workers that come under this category include all

Fig. 2

government servants, municipal employees, teachers, factory workers, plantation workers, those engaged in trade, commerce, business, transport, banking, mining, construction, political or social work, priests, entertainment artists, etc. In fact, all those workers other than cultivators or agricultural labourers or household industry workers are 'Other Workers'. The proportion of female other workers in the total working population in Bareilly district was 24.31 per cent in 2001, which increased to 34.61 per cent in 2011 (Table-2). The highest proportion of female other workers was found in Alampur Jafarabad (46.20%) and Kyara (46.75%) blocks in 2001 and 2011 respectively. This high proportion indicates the presence of greater tertiary activities in these blocks, also proximity to the urban centre has contributed to these areas. The lowest proportion of female other workers was found in Shergarh (8.28%) and Baheri (29.31%) blocks in 2001 and 2011 as these blocks corresponded to higher cultivators and agricultural labourers. Out of 15 blocks two blocks recorded negative growth rate while other 13 blocks recorded positive change during 2001 to 2011. Eight blocks have low (<21%) proportion of female other workers in 2001, while in 2011 not a single block comes in this category. Ten blocks (Richha, Nawabganj, Meerganj, Fatehganj west, Bhojipura, Kyara, Bithrichainpur, Bhadpura, Bhuta and Faridpur) had female other workers upwards of 34% of the total working population in 2011 (Table 2 & Figure 2). The decadal change in Bareilly district in terms of female other workers was 81.09 per cent from 2001 to 2011. The highest and the lowest decadal change were respectively in Bhadpura (567.37%) and Baheri (-68.45%). Two blocks Baheri and Alampur Jafarabad had very low (negative) growth, while the decadal change of female other workers in Nawabganj, Bhadpura and Meerganj is very high (400%) (Table 2 & Fig. 2). The literacy rate of female increased during this period so female are also getting jobs in various private and government sectors.

Conclusion

By the analysis of the female working population, we found that 10.91 percent females count as working population in 2001, while in 2011 it increase to 11.56 percent of total female working population. It is clear that the proportion of main workers is decreasing because some of the small cottage industries have closed or not working in good condition that's why the duration of work is decreasing and the proportion of marginal workers is increasing because most of the people are engaged in building construction, fishing, poultry form, vender, tailor etc. that provide for few days' work. The total population as well as female cultivators are decreased. The main reason of decreasing proportion of cultivators of the total

working population is decreasing because of the low landholding of the peasant, and due to low agricultural income, many cultivators are abandoning farming. That's why the proportion of agricultural labourers is decreasing in all blocks and female agricultural labourers are record positive change except four blocks. But there is a good thing that the proportion of female household industries workers shown very good change because female getting work in their home. But they do not getting proper wages for their work also mos of the female. Other female workers has also grown up because secondary and tertiary occupations have increased of the total working population during 2001 to 2011, which are a very auspicious indication for the economic development of the district. The decreasing workforce in cultivators has been due to the changing in the family structure which causes fragmentation of land and due to which many cultivators either sold their land or given it on lease. The decrease in agricultural labourers has been attributed due to the increasing in other workers category due to higher literacy and less wages in agricultural activities. The increase in household workers category and others workers has attributed due to the change in living standards and higher educational level. The government has also provided job opportunities in many sectors other than primary sectors so the engagement in other activities has an increasing trend.

References

- Census of India (2001). District Census Handbook, Bareilly. <https://censusindia.gov.in>
- Census of India (2011). District Census Handbook, Bareilly. <https://censusindia.gov.in>
- Chakraborty, I., & Chakraborty, A. (2009). Female work participation and gender differential in earning in West Bengal. Institute of Development Studies.
- Chakravarty, S. (1975). Women power in agriculture. *Kurukshetra*, 24(4), 8-9.
- Chaudhary, D. K., & Gownamani, D. (2022). Impact of Literacy on Working Population in Kushinagar District, Uttar Pradesh. *National Geographical Journal of India*, 65(2), 178-186.
- Dasgupta, P., & Goldar, B. (2005). Female labour supply in rural India: An econometric analysis. Delhi: Institute of Economic Growth.
- Devi, G., & Tiwari, S. (2019). Gender disparity in Literacy in Bareilly district. *National Geographical Journal of India*, 65(1), 88-96.
- Fletcher, E., Pande, R., & Moore, C. M. T. (2017). Women and work in India: Descriptive evidence and a review of potential policies.
- Ghai, S. (2018). The anomaly of women's work and education in India (No. 368). Working Paper.
- Heath, R., & Jayachandran, S. (2016). The causes and consequences of increased female education and labor force participation in developing countries (No. w22766). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Ince, M. (2010). How the education affects female labor force? Empirical evidence from Turkey. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 634-639.

- International Labour Organization (2022). Female labor force participation. <https://genderdata.worldbank.org/data-stories/flfp-data>.
- Kapsos, S., Silbermann, A., & Bourmpoula, E. (2014). Why is female labour force participation declining so sharply in India? (pp. 1-51). Geneva: ILO.
- Kaur, P. (2016). Factors Affecting Female Labor Force Participation in North East India. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Studies*, 3(2), 159-166.
- Lahoti, R., & Swaminathan, H. (2013). Economic development and female labor force participation in India. *IIM Bangalore Research Paper*, (414).
- Nath, K. (1970). Female work participation and economic development: A regional analysis. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 846-849.
- Nayyar, R. (1987). Female participation rates in rural India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 2207-2216.
- Sorsa, P., Mares, J., Didier, M., Guimaraes, C., Rabate, M., Tang, G., & Tuske, A. (2015). Determinants of the low female labour force participation in India.
- Tripathy, B., & Raha, S. (2019). A Comparative Analysis between Women Work Participation and Literacy. *Journal of Scientific Computing*, 8 (12), 13

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